

Study on contents of Pyrovatex CP New and Knittex FFRC in flame retardant treatment for cotton fabrics

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Abstract: N-methylol dimethylphosphonopropionamide with labeled Pyrovatex CP New and the crosslinking modified dihydroxy ethylene urea formaldehyde free labeled Knittex FFRC has achieved good flame retardancy for cotton fabrics. In this study, we are interested in the combination of these two compounds at different concentration in the process of flame retardant. There are 9 options were experimented. The fabric samples treated with 3 different concentrations 350, 400 and 450 g/l of Pyrovatex CP New and each of the different concentrations 80, 100, 120 g/l of Knittex FFRC. The flame-retardant efficiency of treated samples and the samples after 20, 30 washing of cycles were evaluated through the characteristics of the 45° flame test. The method was according to ASTM D 1230-94 standard. The results showed that the treated samples after being burned for 9s were self-extinguish, and the char length less than 30 mm. The drapability of samples were tested according to NF G07-109 standard. The finished cotton fabrics were soft.

Keywords: Flame retardant; Cotton; Pyrovatex CP New; Durable; Formaldehyde free.
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1. Introduction

Cotton is a natural vegetable single elongated fiber, developed from an epidermal cell of the cotton seed, which grows in many countries of the world [1]. Cotton fabric is an important textile widely used to produce apparel, home furnishings, and various industrial products due to its characteristics of softness, breathability, and capability to absorb moisture [2]. However, cotton fabric has low fire resistance [3-6]. Cotton fabrics catch fire easily and the flame spreads fast [7]. Therefore, it is necessary to flame retardant treatment for cotton fabric.

Among several chemical finishes being applied to impart FR properties to cotton fabrics, very few create finished fabrics that can withstand FR properties after being laundered several times. N- methylol dimethyl phosphonopropionamide (MDPA) is among the major FR materials utilized for the cotton fabrics [8], which reacts with cellulose hydroxyl groups and forms covalent bond. These compounds affect the themolysis, prevent the formation of levoglucosan and flammable volatiles, and promote the formation

2.2.2 Flame retardant treatment process

In this study, the fabric samples 35x 35cm were impregnated with finishing solution with different chemical concentrations (Shown in Table 2). The fabrics were padded through two nips to reach an average wet pickup of 80% by padder SDL D394A, then the samples were dried at 110 °C for 5 minutes, and the cured time is 180°C for 2 minutes. The stenter SDL D398 was used for drying and curing steps. Finally, the samples were washed under running water for 5 minutes and dried in the stenter at 110 °C for 3 minutes. The treated samples were stored in the polyethylene bags and in the standard laboratory conditions for 24 hours before any further analysis.

Table 2. The bath formulations

Sample code	PR (g/l)	K (g/l)	Tenside (g/l)
S1	350	80	5
S2	350	100	5
S3	350	120	5
S4	400	80	5
S5	400	100	5
S6	400	120	5
S7	450	80	5
S8	450	100	5
S9	450	120	5

2.2.3 Washing of treated samples

The treated samples were washed in accordance with ISO-6330 standard clause 6A [10]. This study aims to determine the flame retardant durability of the treated fabric. This process added non phosphate ECE reference detergent A, and tested by the Electrolux EW 1290W front load washing machine. After the end 20 and 30 of washing cycles, the samples are retained to test the flammability of samples.

The flame retardant finishing and the washing process were carried out at chemical textile LAB of Hanoi University of Science and Technology (HUST)

2.2.4 Flammability test

The flame retardant treated samples were tested on a 45° flammability tester according to ASTM D 1230-94 [11] procedure to observe ignition times, char length, after-flame and after-glow of the samples. The test was carried out at chemical textile LAB of Hanoi University of Science and Technology.

2.2.5 Determination of drapability

AFNOR - NF G07-109 [12] Tests for fabrics- Method for determination of the drape of a woven or knitted fabric. There are control and 3 samples with different chemical content that have been tested drapability (S1, S5 and S9)

3. Results

3.1 The flammability of finished cotton fabrics.

The flame resistances of the control and finished cotton fabric samples were assessed by the characteristics of 45° flammability test. The result shows in Table 3, Figure 1

Table 3 and Figure 1 show that the control sample burned strongly after direct exposure to the ignition source. The ignition time was only 3 seconds. After removing the combustion source, the sample continued to burn and after-flame was 36s. After extinguishing, there was 9 s of after-glow, and the cotton fabric almost completely burned out without any remains. In contrast, during the flame testing, the treated sample self-extinguished immediately while the flame was removed. No after-flame and after-glow were observed and the ignition times were 9 seconds (3 times longer than the untreated sample, Figure 2).

The results in Table 3 and Figures 1b, 1c and 1d showed that the treated samples created char with a length of less than 3cm. Thus, the flame resistance of the cotton fabric was enhanced with the applied flame retardant finish.

Table 3. 45° flammability characteristics of control, treated samples

Sample	Ignition times (s)	After-flame (s)	After-glow (s)	Char length (mm)	Number of washing cycle
Control	3	36	9	Completely burned	
S1	9	0	0	27 ± 1	0
S2	9	0	0	26 ± 1	
S3	9	0	0	27 ± 2	
S4	9	0	0	27 ± 1	
S5	9	0	0	26 ± 1	
S6	9	0	0	26 ± 2	
S7	9	0	0	26 ± 1	
S8	9	0	0	27± 1	
S9	9	0	0	26 ± 2	
S1	9	0	0	27 ± 1	
S2	9	0	0	26 ± 2	
S3	9	0	0	26 ± 3	
S4	9	0	0	26 ± 2	
S5	9	0	0	26 ± 2	20
S6	9	0	0	26 ± 1	
S7	9	0	0	26 ± 3	
S8	9	0	0	26± 2	
S9	9	0	0	26 ± 2	
S1	9	0	0	27 ± 1	
S2	9	0	0	26 ± 1	
S3	9	0	0	26 ± 2	
S4	9	0	0	26 ± 1	
S5	9	0	0	26 ± 2	30

S6	9	0	0	26 ± 1
S7	9	0	0	26 ± 1
S8	9	0	0	26 ± 2
S9	9	0	0	26 ± 3

Figure 1. The results 45° flammability test of control; 20, 30 of washing cycle and treated samples

Figure 2. The Ignition times of control; No washing (0 OWC); 20 of washing cycles (20 OWC), and 30 of washing cycles (30 OWC) samples

3.2 Drapability of the control and treated fabrics.

The result in Table 4 shows the drapability of the original and the cotton fabrics finished with different concentrations of Pyrovatex CP New and Knittex FFRC. After treatment, the drapability of the fabric was almost unchanged. The treated cotton fabrics remained soft. These small changes in Drapage coefficient do not have a practical impact on the product. No color distortion of the fabric was observed owing to the flame retardant finish application.

Table 4. Drapage coefficient of control and treated cotton fabrics

Sample	Drapage coefficient of reverse D (%)	Drapage coefficient of the face D (%)	The average value of Drapage coefficient D (%)
Control	56,26	56,73	56,49
400-100	56,95	57,87	57,41
450-120	55,56	56,12	55,84
350-80	53,87	54,57	54,22

4. Discussion

The results from this study show that Pyrovatex CP New provides durable flame retardancy on cotton fabric. The char formation of treated samples may be due to the phosphorus-based flame retardant, which promoted the dehydration of the cotton fabric when the fabric was thermally decomposed [9]. There was virtually no difference in the char length of the samples treated with 9 different finishing solutions for up to 20, 30 of washing cycles. This suggests that Knittex FFRC and Pyrovatex CP New are a durable crosslinking and flame retardant agents in finishing treatment for cotton fabrics. In addition, the treated cotton fabrics remained soft.

On the other hand, the 45° flammability test is not severe enough to assess the difference in the ability flame retardant of cotton fabric when was treated with different concentration of PR and K. Therefore, there is a need for other studies such as vertical flammability test, TGA or LOI, and so on in order to assess their difference.

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